

Analysing Architectural Floor Plans Using Keras-OCR

Milan RJ
PG Scholar
Dept. Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
milanrj@mca.ajce.in

Dr. Paulin Paul
Asst. Professor
Dept. Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
paulinepaul@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Architectural floor plans are documents that result from an iterative design process to define the layout distribution of a building. Here the overall structure plays a crucial role in the total building design. In the present scenario looking into the design plan, workers identify requirement of total number of sprinklers for the entire building. But this can be automated by analyzing floor plan images and recognizing their measurements through machine learning approaches to precisely predict the requirements. The exact selection of required no of sprinklers is important for fire and safety and automatic discharge of water usually from pipes laid along the ceiling. This proposed work intends to automate and implement a new approach to analyze floor plan and calculate the area of the floor plan and predict the approximate number of sprinklers needed to be placed in the ceiling that assumes to improve the safety. This methodology proposes to use machine learning approach using Keras-ocr

Keywords: Keras-ocr , Matplotlib , Pyplot , NumPy , Architectural floor plan

I. INTRODUCTION

Architectural floor plan analysis is an extensive process that involves analysing a given floor plan image in order to retrieve the corresponding semantic information. They contain structural and semantic data, such as room types and sizes. In the current scenario, workers examine the floor plan and determine the total area of the building and calculate the number of sprinklers required for the entire building. However, as a solution this can be automated. This paper introduces a method for analysing floorplan images using a powerful optical character recognition tool named Keras-OCR. With just a few lines of code, you can extract text with Keras-OCR.

Here we are extracting the measurements from the image and calculating the area of the entire building using the given floor plan and predicting the no sprinklers need to be installed in the building. For calculating the area of the building from architectural floor plan we are retrieving information from the corresponding semantic data of the given cells in the plan and multiplying the length and width measurements and adding the individual measurements of each cells together. Now, we divide the building's entire area by 150 to determine the total number of sprinklers required. We automate this process using required libraries.

The given fig [1], describes the architecture of KerasOCR.

In the given architecture, the input image, or the floor plan in the case of the research done in this paper is inputted. This image is then pre-processed to remove unwanted noises and then the textual information is detected and recognized from the inputted image. On performing the required operations, we get the required output.

Fig.1. Architecture of keras-ocr

II. EXISTING AND PROPOSED SYSYTEM

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is a field that has been studied for decades. OCR is a technique for extracting data from a record image that also provides full alphanumeric recognition of printed or handwritten characters, text numerical, letters, and symbols into a computer processable format such as ASCII, Unicode, and so on. It is widely used in our daily activities because it saves time and has a predetermined speed level. Image acquisition, pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, training a neural network, and post-processing are all steps in OCR. Many OCR methods are available in data extraction tools such as Nanonets, DocParser, Adobe Acrobat, and many others.

All the modules for architectural floor plan detection are as follows

- Importing keras - ocr
- Extracting text from image using keras ocr
- Plotting image using matplotlib and numpy

- Removing the noise by excluding the unwanted data from the extracted text.
- Calculating the total area of the entire building by extracting the measurements
- Calculating the number of sprinklers needed for the building

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The platform used to run the research done in this paper is Google Colab. Colab is a platform that allows anybody to write and execute python code on the basics of machine learning. Google Colab allows you to write and run the code as well as see the output in the same notebook

The libraries used for the proposed system are as follows

- **Keras-ocr**

Keras-OCR is a powerful library for extracting text with a few lines of code. It is a viable choice for free image text extraction. Optical Character Recognition is the term denoted by the abbreviation "OCR." Text extraction from photographs is a common technique known as "Text Recognition." The Backend library is used to resolve it because it is unable to handle low-level computations. By acting as a high-level API wrapper for the low-level API, the backend library enables it to run on TensorFlow, CNTK, or Theano. It also offers pre-built OCR models and a pipeline for training new OCR models from beginning to end.

- **Matplotlib**

Matplotlib is a plotting library available as a component of NumPy, a big data numerical handling resource, for the Python programming language. Plots are embedded in Python programs using Matplotlib's object-oriented API. Although matplotlib has to deal with numbers, its usefulness is specifically related to visual charting tools. These materials are therefore conceptually more analytical than generating. All of this infrastructure, however, functions as a unit to enable the machine learning programs to generate output that is helpful to human handlers.

- **Pyplot**

pyplot is a set of functions that makes matplotlib behave like MATLAB. Each pyplot function modifies a figure in some way, such as by creating a figure, a plotting area within a figure, plotting some lines within a plotting area, decorating the plot with labels, and so on.

- **NumPy**

NumPy is a python library used to manipulate arrays. It can be applied to arrays to carry out a wide range of

mathematical operations. It provides a sizable library of advanced mathematical functions that work with these arrays and matrices in addition to enhancing Python with strong data structures that ensure effective calculations with arrays and matrices. In contrast to lists, NumPy arrays are stored in a single continuous location in memory, making it very easy for programmers to access and manipulate them.

- **Build Model**

The steps involved in the building model are:

- i. Installing keras-ocr
- ii. Importing keras-ocr , pyplot , numpy

```
[26] import keras_ocr # an library in keras ,keras ocr
      from matplotlib import pyplot as plt #ploting lib
      import numpy as np #for highlevel mathematical functions
```

- iii. Importing the images to be tested

```
[27] images = [ keras_ocr.tools.read(url) for url in [
            '/content/MILAN1 (1).jpg', '/content/floorplan17.jpeg'
        ]]
```

- iv. Displaying the image to be detected

- v. Box plotting and predicting the text from the image

```
pipeline = keras_ocr.pipeline.Pipeline() # linear series of data transforms to be linked together
prediction_groups = pipeline.recognize(images)
fig, axes = plt.subplots(nrows=len(images), figsize=(20, 20))
for ax, image, predictions in zip(axes, images, prediction_groups):
    keras_ocr.tools.drawAnnotations(image=image, predictions=predictions, ax=ax)
```


- vi. Calculating the total area of the building and finding the no of sprinklers required

Keras-ocr predict each text as string. Since each measurements are in the format “length x width,” we concatenate each string using “x”. Later we split the concatenated string to list by splitting using split function `split(“x”)`.

Now, we remove the noise data i.e, all the string elements from the list and we calculate the total area of the building using the measurements from the list and finally the total number of sprinklers needed is calculated using the equation

$$\text{sprinklers} = \text{ceil}(\text{area}/150)$$

by the fact that each sprinkler should be placed 150m apart.

```
[31] s=""
pred_image = prediction_groups[0];
for text, box in pred_image:
    s = s+text+"x" # s string text concatenate with x
    #print(text)
    #print(s)

import math
list1 = []
area=0
li = list(s.split("x")) # splitting elements by x
#print(li)
m = [s for s in li if s.isdigit()] #DIGITS ONLY
#print(m)
#len(m)
for i in range(0, len(m), 2):
    list1.append(int(m[i])*int(m[i+1])) #multiplying the i and i+1
#print(list1)
for i in range(len(list1)):
    area += list1[i]
print("The total sq feet of the building is "+str(area))
sprinklers = math.ceil(area/150)
print("No.of sprinklers needed "+str(sprinklers))
```

The total sq feet of the building is 735
No.of sprinklers needed 6

IV.CONCLUSION

To conclude, this research paper aims to provide the customer with a cost-effective as well as a low time-consuming approach to calculate the area floor plan by just analyzing the floor plan and extracting the information regarding the dimensions of each rooms using Optical Character Recognition. Keras-ocr along with other python packages provide the path to automate and calculate the

area of the floor plan as well as the precise number of sprinklers required to be placed in the ceiling for safety measures.

The study done in this paper aims to mainly find the easiest and most sturdy methods to make it the most customer-friendly. Box plotting makes it facile to bound as well as calculate the measures easily. Finally, this paper concludes that the research methods done are the finest for the required needs.

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